

FABRICATION AND MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF GLASS MATRIX COMPOSITES WITH DIFFERENT FIBRE ARCHITECTURES

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SUMMARY: Processing routes have been developed for the fabrication of glass matrix composites with 2-dimensional woven fibre mats as reinforcement. Carbon and metallic (stainless steel 316L) fibre mats were investigated. In order to achieve infiltration of the matrix material into the fibres tows and an adequate adhesion between matrix and fibres, an electrophoretic deposition (EPD) technique was used. The infiltration capability using both a glass powder suspension and a silica colloidal solution was investigated and compared. Thus, the processing routes involve three steps: 1) the infiltration of the fibre mats using electrophoretic deposition, 2) the preparation of composite green bodies by stacking of infiltrated prepregs and 3) the consolidation of the composites by a high-temperature densification process involving pressureless sintering or hot-pressing. A high-level of matrix infiltration in the intra-tow regions was achieved when a silica colloidal solution was used. These samples could be densified by pressureless sintering. On the other hand, when a glass powder suspension was used, there was not complete infiltration of the fibre mats. Porosity in these samples could not be eliminated even after a hot-pressing stage.

KEYWORDS: glass matrix composites, woven fibre reinforcement, electrophoresis, composites processing, metallic fibre reinforcement, hot-pressing, sintering

INTRODUCTION

The brittle nature, and therefore, high susceptibility to catastrophic failure of glass and glass-ceramic materials limits their use in structural applications. One approach to the improvement of the thermomechanical properties of these materials is to produce a composite. In this way, the low-modulus, low-strength, brittle matrix is reinforced by a high-modulus, high-strength and/or high-ductility second constituent in the form of continuous or chopped fibres, whiskers, platelets or particulates [1].

The best results in terms of increasing the fracture tolerance and imparting a pseudo-ductile fracture behaviour to brittle matrices is achieved with continuous fibre reinforcement [1,2]. The vast majority of work concerned with fibre reinforcement of glasses and glass-ceramics has focused on using ceramic fibres, especially in unidirectional and cross-ply fibre alignments [2-7]. The reinforcement of glass matrices by 2-dimensional fibre architectures, including ductile (metallic) fibre preforms, has been much less investigated [8], despite the advantages that these architectures may have over their unidirectional counterparts. These are related to the more isotropic mechanical properties obtained with 2-dimensional reinforcing elements over unidirectional fibre reinforcement [9].

The use of metallic reinforcement may have still further advantages, including an improved resistance to fibre damage during composite processing due to the intrinsic ductility of metallic fibres and the possibility of exploiting their plastic deformation for composite toughness enhancement [10]. However, the authors are only aware of the work of Russian workers on the use of 2-dimensional metallic fibre mats to reinforce glasses [8].

When using fibre mats as reinforcement, it is normally extremely difficult to achieve complete infiltration of the matrix material into the fibre tows, where the openings are of the order of ≤ 100 nm. Electrophoretic deposition (EPD) of colloidal ceramic sols has been shown recently to be a simple and inexpensive method for achieving complete infiltration of tightly woven fibre preforms [9, 11,12].

The technique has been employed for infiltrating silica and alumina sols into ceramic fibre preforms, such as SiC (Nicalon) [9,11] and alumina woven mats [12], showing that EPD provides a more efficient infiltration and stronger adhesion between fibre and matrix than a simple slurry dipping technique.

In the present study processing routes to fabricate two types of glass matrix composites with 2-dimensional woven fibre mats as reinforcement are developed. Carbon and metallic (stainless steel 316L) fibre mats were investigated. EPD was used to deposit matrix material onto the fibre preforms. For the metallic fibre mat reinforced composites, which were consolidated by pressureless sintering of the glass matrix, a silica sol was used first to infiltrate the metallic fibre mats.

It was anticipated that the silica infiltration would not only contribute to reduce the intra-tow porosity but also, acting as coating for the metallic fibres, would minimise possible reactions of the metal with the glass matrix during high-temperature densification and would provide an adequate interface in order to improve the composite fracture behaviour. A borosilicate glass powder suspension was used to fabricate the carbon fibre mats reinforced composites.

The results of the EPD technique for both the colloidal silica and the glass powder suspension were compared in terms of their ability to infiltrate woven fibre mats.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

Figure 1 shows the processing routes employed in this study to fabricate glass matrix composite materials. The details are given below.

Materials

Woven carbon fibre reinforced composites

Commercially available (Tenax, Akzo AG) woven carbon fibre mats were used, with a fibre diameter of $\approx 10\mu\text{m}$. The glass matrix employed was a borosilicate glass (DURAN, Schott Glaswerke, Mainz, Germany). The glass powder was milled and sieved so that all particles were $< 40\mu\text{m}$. The density of this glass is 2.2 g/cm^3 and its thermal expansion coefficient is $3.3 \times 10^{-6}\text{ 1/}^\circ\text{C}$ [13]. DURAN glass was chosen because it is a well-known matrix material for the fabrication of glass matrix composites [3] and because its viscous flow and sintering behaviour are known [13]. For the EPD experiments a powder aqueous suspension containing

≈40vol% solid and ≈0.1 wt% PVA was prepared. The suspension exhibited a strong tendency to sedimentation.

Woven metal fibre reinforced composites

From the variety of metal fabrics commercially available [14], a woven satin 100% 316L stainless steel fabric (Bekitherm FA, Bekaert SA, Zwevegem, Belgium) was chosen, on the basis of its suitability to be infiltrated by sol particles using electrophoretic deposition. There are other fibre mats available also, made from alloys such as Inconel 601, which have better high temperature properties than 316L, but for this study, the more cost-effective 316L stainless steel was considered adequate to demonstrate the use of this particular processing technology. The individual fibres have an average diameter of 14 μm and the weaves have a nominal thickness of 0.4 mm [14]. The maximum using temperature of the 316L fibres in an oxidising atmosphere is 900°C and the thermal expansion coefficient (20-700°C) is $16.8 \times 10^{-6} \text{ 1/}^\circ\text{C}$ [15,16].

Figure 1: Processing route for the fabrication of 2-dimensional woven fibre mat reinforced glass matrix composites

Due to this relatively low thermal capability and limited oxidation resistance of the metallic fibre used, a glass with low sintering temperature was chosen for the matrix. The glass selected was a soda-lime glass, with a composition corresponding to that used in the German flat glass production [17]. The density of the glass is 2.51 g/cm^3 and it was available as a powder with an average particle size of $\approx 80 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$. Its sintering and pressureless densification behaviour have been investigated previously and an optimised sintering temperature of 670°C was determined [17]. The thermal expansion coefficient of this glass is $9.8 \times 10^{-6} \text{ 1/}^\circ\text{C}$. A commercially available silica sol (Nyacol 2040 NH4, Akzo-PQ Silica, Amersfoort, The Netherlands) was used for the electrophoretic infiltration of the metallic fibre mats. This sol is

stable at pH 9, has a solid content of 40vol% and the sol particles are spherical with an average particle diameter of 20 nm. For the EPD experiments the sol was used as-received.

Infiltration of Fibre Mats by Electrophoretic Deposition (EPD)

The EPD process relies on the presence of small charged particles within a liquid suspension, which, on the application of an electric field, will migrate toward and deposit on an electrode [18]. Movement of the particle occurs because the particle surface is charged with respect to the suspending medium. If the deposition electrode is replaced with a conducting fibre preform, the suspended particles are attracted to the fibre preform and then deposited on and within it. The movement of the ceramic particles in an aqueous suspension under an external applied electric field will be governed mainly by factors such as the field strength, the pH of the solution and the ionic strength of the solution [18]. In the present experiments, both the glass powder particles and the silica particles were negatively charged, as they migrated to the positive electrode.

Thus, the fibre mats were placed as the anode. A stainless steel plate served as the negative electrode. For the DURAN glass powder suspension a voltage of 30 V was applied to the electrodes that were 30mm separated. For the silica sol a much lower voltage (4 V) for the same electrodes separation was found to be adequate to obtain a reasonable deposition rate, in agreement with previous studies using SiC fibre mats [9,11]. The deposition time was varied to find the optimum time for the complete infiltration of the sol into the intra-tow regions, and for obtaining the desired thickness of the deposited layer in the case of the glass powder.

Controlled drying of the infiltrated/coated fibre mats is critical to the production of prepregs of sufficient quality, minimising the generation of cracks. The powder coated fibre mats were dried in normal atmosphere as no significant microcracking was expected due to the large powder particle sizes. The sol infiltrated fibre mats were dried both in normal air and in a humid atmosphere to investigate the effect of drying conditions on microcracking development. The dried fibre mats were impregnated with a vacuum resin and polished to a 1 μm finish for scanning electron microscopy (SEM) examination. For the silica sol infiltrated mats, SEM energy dispersive X-ray analysis (EDX) was employed to differentiate between resin and silica in the intra-tow regions.

Forming of Green Bodies, Composite Consolidation, and Mechanical Tests

Woven carbon fibre reinforced composites

A hot-pressing densification stage was chosen for the consolidation of these composites, as it was found (see Results below) that the EPD process did not yield complete infiltration of the woven carbon fibre mats. Typically, ten coated fibre mats were stapled, introduced in a graphite die and hot-pressed in vacuum at 900°C under an applied pressure of 10 MPa. The holding time was 30 minutes. In this way cylindrical samples (50 mm diameter, \approx 5.4 mm height) were obtained. From these samples test bars (5 x 4 x 40 mm) were prepared by cutting and polishing. These bars were tested in three-point bending (30 mm span). The load-displacement diagram was recorded and SEM was used to observe fracture surfaces.

Woven metal fibre reinforced composites

The silica sol-infiltrated metallic fibre mats were used to prepare a glass matrix composite by a simple uniaxial cold-pressing and sintering route. Typically, two fibre mats were sandwiched between layers of the soda-lime glass matrix powder in a die (24 mm diameter) to form the green bodies. Similar laminated composites, but containing woven fabrics of Si-Ti-C-O fibres sandwiched between thin mullite layers have been reported in the literature [19]. Uniaxial pressures of 90 MPa were employed to obtain samples of sufficient strength to be handled. The specimens were heated at a rate of 10°C/min up to the sintering temperature of 670°C and the dwell time at temperature was 1 hour before a subsequent furnace cooling stage.

The samples were fabricated solely to investigate the possibility of composite consolidation by this simple, pressureless densification route, and to assess the presence of any reaction at the silica/metal fibre and silica/ glass matrix interfaces. Selected sintered samples were cut, polished and observed using SEM. In addition, several rectangular bars (20mm x 2mm x 3mm) were cut from the cylinders and used to investigate, in a qualitative manner, the fracture behaviour of the composites in three-point flexion (span: 16 mm). Fracture surfaces were observed using SEM.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Woven Carbon Fibre Reinforced Composites

Figure 2 is a SEM micrograph showing the microstructure of a woven carbon fibre reinforced DURAN glass matrix composite after hot-pressing at 900 °C. A poor infiltration of glass matrix in the spaces between the fibres is observed. This means that the combination of EPD and hot-pressing, as employed in this study, was unsuitable for obtaining pore-free materials. Indeed, using a suspension of μm -sized glass particles in the EPD cell was the reason why the fibre mats could not be infiltrated fully, and the glass particles were only (firmly) adhered to the surfaces of the fibre mat. Moreover, the viscosity of the glass at the hot-pressing temperature (900 °C) was not sufficiently low to allow an efficient infiltration. This effect may be enhanced by a poor wettability of the carbon fibres by the viscous glass. Figure 3 shows the load-displacement diagramme of a sample during the three-point bending test.

Composite behaviour, i.e. non-catastrophic fracture, is observed. However, due to the considerable porosity present, the absolute values of the mechanical properties achieved are rather low. The optimization of the hot-pressing parameters should result in a reduction of the intra- and inter-tow porosity in these samples and the attainment of better mechanical properties. These properties should be comparable to those measured in commercially available unidirectional carbon fibre reinforced DURAN glass matrix composites (ultimate fracture strength = 800-1200 MPa, Young's modulus = 120 GPa [3]), with the advantage, however, of being isotropic in 2 dimensions due to the particular fibre architecture used. It is suggested, however, that an increase of the hot-pressing pressure will not necessarily lead to better results in terms of glass infiltration, since this would tend to close the intra-and inter-tow spaces, making more difficult the flow and intra-tow penetration of the glass. Probably a pre-treatment of the carbon fibres surfaces to improve their wettability by the viscous glass would be an effective approach.

Fig. 2: SEM micrograph showing the microstructure of a carbon fibre mat reinforced DURAN glass matrix composite. Poor infiltration of the matrix in the spaces between the fibres is observed

Fig. 3: Load-displacement diagramme for a carbon fibre mat reinforced glass matrix composite during a three-point bending test

Woven metal fibre reinforced composites

Figures 4a and 4b show SEM micrographs of a metallic fibre mat infiltrated with silica sol, at low and high magnification, respectively. The SEM images demonstrate that the EPD technique was capable of producing a high level of sol infiltration into the electrically conducting fibre tows. It is suggested that the infiltration process is enhanced by the opening up of the spaces in the fibre tow through the mutual repulsion of the charged fibres. Owing to the small particle size of the silica sol used (20 nm), the particles are able to infiltrate the spaces between the fibre tows efficiently. In addition, the use of a relatively low EPD voltage minimised the electrolyte decomposition and subsequent hydrogen and oxygen gas evolution found to occur in previous work on EPD of silica sols [9].

Fig. 4: SEM micrographs of an impregnated metallic fibre mat, showing that during EPD the silica particles have infiltrated fully the intra-tow regions, a) low and b) high magnification (F: Fibre, M: electrophoretically deposited silica).

As in all sol-gel preparation methods, control of the drying stage is important to reduce the likelihood of drying cracks being generated. The presence of such microcracks is apparent in

Figure 4 and they occur due to the differential shrinkage of the gel network, which generates tensile stresses at the surface and leads to the growth of microscopic flaws [20]. As mentioned before, no cracks were generated in the carbon fibre mats that were coated with the glass powder. Thus, when a sol is used, the selection of the appropriate drying method and the thickness of the deposited layer are critical factors in the preparation of high-quality prepregs for composite fabrication. A deposition time of 1 min was found here to be sufficient for the complete infiltration of the sol into the intra- and inter-tow regions, and for obtaining the desired thickness of the deposited layer. It was found also, that the deposition time has no effect on the quality of the intra-tow impregnation, in agreement with previous studies on SiC woven fibre mats [9,11]. Fibre mats that were impregnated using EPD times of 1 minute contained small cracks after drying in a normal atmosphere, whereas, the prepregs prepared by slow drying in a humid atmosphere (80% humidity) exhibited no crack formation in between the fibres. The cracks formed during air drying were, however, very narrow because the deposited film was extremely thin.

A more detailed investigation of the densification behaviour and microstructural characteristics of the woven metal fibre reinforced glass composites has been given elsewhere [21]. Although with the present samples the mechanical properties could not be evaluated quantitatively, observation of the fracture surfaces of the bars broken in flexion supplies some information on the fracture behaviour of the material. Figure 5 shows a typical fracture surface. The sample failed in a “graceful”, i.e. non-catastrophic, manner and pull-out of the fibres was observed. This mechanism is compatible with the presence of a weak interface. However, the pull-out lengths are short, and some deformation of the fibres can be seen also in the micrograph. Thus, this preliminary result seems to indicate that in the present composites, both plastic deformation of the reinforcement and frictional sliding between the fibres and the glass matrix can be utilised for toughness improvement. It has been shown in the literature [22], that an optimum interfacial bonding strength is essential to exploit both the aforementioned toughening mechanisms. The presence of the porous silica coating in the present composites would seem to be responsible for this behaviour. It is suggested that the silica particles provide i) sufficient interfacial strength for load transfer between the matrix and the fibres due to the fact that they are adhered to the metallic fibre by the EPD process, and ii) the weaker interfacial bonding necessary for the fibre pull-out behaviour. This last requirement is achieved due to the partial densification of the silica coating and the presence of drying-induced microcracks, which cannot be closed during the pressureless densification process. These suggestions, however, need to be verified by a proper characterisation of the interfaces and by a detailed study of the fracture behaviour of the composites, which is the focus of current research.

Fig. 5: SEM micrograph of the fracture surface of a metallic fibre reinforced glass matrix composite fractured in flexion. Pull-out of the fibres can be seen, as well as some deformation at the fibre ends.

CONCLUSIONS

Processing routes have been presented for the fabrication of glass matrix composites containing 2-dimensional fibre reinforcement. Both woven carbon and metallic (316L SS) fibre mats were used. The composite fabrication involves the use of electrophoretic deposition to infiltrate and coat the fibre mats. The infiltration capability using both a glass powder suspension and a silica colloidal solution was investigated and compared. A high-level of infiltration in the intra-tow regions was achieved when a silica colloidal solution was used. These samples could be densified by pressureless sintering. Although the mechanical properties of these samples were not determined, the observation of fracture surfaces revealed that both fibre pull-out and fibre deformation occur, which should lead to a significant toughness enhancement. For the carbon fibre mat containing composites, the glass powder suspension used for EPD did not yield complete infiltration of the fibre mats. To reduce porosity, these samples had to be densified by hot-pressing. The hot-pressing parameters need to be optimised, however, as residual porosity was still present in the samples. The poor wettability of the carbon fibres by the viscous glass at the working temperature may enhance the lack of penetration of the glass into the intra- and inter-tow spaces.

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